

FATTY OIL OF THE SEEDS OF *IPOMOEA MURICATA* JACQ. (N.O. CONVULVULACEAE)

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The seeds of *Ipomoea muricata*, Jacq. on extraction with ether gave a fatty oil (8.7%). The component acids of the fatty oil have been shown to be palmitic (13.61%), stearic acid (22.55%), behenic acid (3.78%), linolenic acid (3.92%), linolic acid (15.15%) and oleic acid (40.97%).

Our recent observation regarding the occurrence of behenic acid to the extent of 6.64% in the fatty oil from the seeds of *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet, (N. O. Convolvulaceae) has led us to the study of other fatty oils from the seeds of plants belonging to the same natural order. The present paper deals with the chemical examination of the fatty oil from the seeds of *Ipomoea muricata* Jacq. (N. O. Convolvulaceae).

Ipomoea muricata, Jacq. is a climber, commonly known as *Bhonvari*. It is known by the following names in different Indian languages: Small *Bhonvari* (Marathi), *Mirchi* (Hindi and Bengalee) and *Garayo* (Gujarathi.) It is an annual creeper growing in the rainy season. It has blue bell-shaped flowers. The seeds have three sides, two of which are plane and one convex. The seeds are black in colour when mature. The fruits and the seeds of this creeper are just similar to those of *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet.

The juice of the green leaves is used against bed bugs as it is believed to have insect-repellent properties. The seeds are said to be used as a purgative (cf. Desai, "Materia Medica and Therapeutics of Indian Medicinal Plants").

The seeds yield an oil (8.74%) when extracted with petroleum ether or sulphuric ether. The fatty acids of the oil have been separated into solid and liquid acids according to the usual procedure. The mixed fatty acids are found to have palmitic (13.6%), stearic (22.5%), behenic (3.78%), linolenic (3.91%), linolic (15.2%) and oleic acid (40.97%).

Hilditch ("The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", Chapman and Hall, 1940, p. 311) has remarked "Behenic acid is the chief constituent of behen oil. It is possibly present in very small proportions in a number of seed fats for example in groundnut oil, rapeseed oil and perhaps in other cruciferous seed oils. In none of these instances does it form more than 1% of the mixed fatty acids of the seed fat". The only other seed fat in which behenic acid occurs to a greater extent is *Parkia* seed fat investigated by Paranjape (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1931, 8, 767). In the light of these observations the presence of behenic acid to the extent of 3.784% in the fatty oil from the seeds of *Ipomoea muricata*, Jacq and to the extent of 6.64% in the fatty oil from *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet (vide this issue, p. 83) is worth recording. But it may be noted that these two plants belong to Convolvulaceae, while *Parkia* seeds belong to N.O. Leguminosae.

Very few seeds from plants belonging to the N. O. Convolvulaceae have been studied. Some species of *Ipomoea* including *maricata* have been examined by Kassner (*Pharm. J.*, 1924, 112, 328). Kassner states that oils from these species have similar physical and chemical properties and are very similar to one another. Detailed examination of the oils, however, has not been carried out. Beside the seed oils of *Argyria speciosa*, Sweet and *Ipomoea muricata*, Jacq, the only other seed oil from plants belonging to this natural order which has been analysed is the seed oil from *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb. (Agarwall and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 264) but according to these authors it does not contain behenic acid. It is necessary therefore to study a number of seed oils of plants belonging to the N. O. Convolvulaceae before making a generalisation that the seed oils of plants belonging to Convolvulaceae contain behenic acid as one of the component acids.

Unsaponifiable matter from the seed oil of *Ipomoea muricata*, Jacq. is obtained in a crystalline form after several crystallisations from alcohol and melts at 131–52° (acetyl derivative, m. p. 119°). It gives all the colour reactions characteristics of phytosterols. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Physical and Chemical Properties of the Oil.—The finely powdered seeds (500 g.) were extracted with ether (sulphuric). The oil obtained had the following constants.

TABLE I

Density at 30°	...	0.9164	Saponifica-	
Refractive index at 30°	...	1.45288	tion value	...
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	82.57	Acid value	...
				200.0
				1696

Mixed Fatty Acids—The oil (40 g.) was saponified with sodium hydroxide. The soap after removing the alcohol was dried and extracted with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The soap free from the unsaponifiable was dissolved in water and acidified with sulphuric acid. The liberated fatty acids were separated from water and dried. The mixed fatty acids are semi solid and have iodine value (Hanus), 76.0; equiv. wt. 286.0; titre test, 40.5.

Separation of the Mixed Acids.—The solid and liquid acids were separated by Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method. The following table gives the percentage, equivalent weight and iodine value of the saturated and unsaturated acids.

TABLE II

	M.p.	Percentage	Equiv. wt.	I. V.
Solid acids (saturated)	55–56°	40	265.6	0.1
Liquid acids (unsaturated)		60	280.0	127.1

Identification of Solid Acids.—Methyl esters of the solid acids were prepared by Fischer Speier method and the esters (8.7 g.) were fractionally distilled at 15 mm. pressure.

The results of fractionation of the methyl esters of the solid acids are given in the following table.

TABLE III

Fraction No.	B. p.	Wt.	Sapon. value.	Mean M. W.
I	Up to 200°	2.84 g.	207	257.1
II	200°-206°	1.6	189.42	283.6
III	206°-210°	2.84	183.2	290.6
IV	210°-225°	1.0	176.0	303.3
Residue	—	0.26	—	—

Fraction I.—This fraction on hydrolysis in the usual manner gave an acid having equivalent weight 257 and m. p. 60°. On crystallisation from alcohol it had m. p. 61-61.5° and equivalent weight 256. The mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of palmitic acid was unchanged. Hence this fraction contains methyl palmitate only.

Fraction II.—Hydrolysis of this fraction gave an acid, m. p. 65° and equivalent weight 283.4. On crystallisation it had m.p. 68-69° and equivalent weight 284, showing that this fraction consists of methyl stearate only.

Fractions III and IV.—These fractions were hydrolysed and the liberated acids had m.p. and equivalent weight as shown below. The acids from each of these fractions were separated into different fractions by fractional precipitation of their magnesium salts. The acids were dissolved in just sufficient quantity of alcohol and neutralised with sodium hydroxide.

Then magnesium acetate solution was added to precipitate a fraction of the total acids. The precipitated magnesium salt was separated, decomposed with hydrochloric acid and free acids were obtained in the usual manner. The following table gives equivalent weights and melting points of the acids from the filtrates and precipitates.

TABLE IV

	Fraction III	Filtrate IIIa	Precipitate. IIIb	Fraction IV	Filtrate IV a	Precipitate. IV b
Equiv. wt.	290.6	268	229	303.3	283.4	231.9
M.p.	58°	66°	70°	60°	65°	70-71°

Fractions III (a) and IV (a) were identified as stearic acids by their equivalent weight and mixed melting point with an authentic specimen.

Fractions III (b) and IV (b) were mixed together and further fractionally precipitated as magnesium salt. The filtrate from the precipitation had m.p. 66° which on crystallisation was raised to 67°. The acids from the precipitated magnesium salts on the other hand had m.p. 77.5° which on recrystallisation was raised to 79-80°. The acid from the precipitated magnesium salts was further crystallised from alcohol when it melted at 80-81°, thus proving the presence of behenic acid. The fractions III and IV therefore contain methyl stearate and methyl behenate.

Residue.—As the quantity of the residue was very small (0.26 g.), the acid could not be identified and it was neglected in calculating the composition of the mixed fatty acids. The following table gives the composition of various fractions of methyl esters.

TABLE V

Fraction No.	Palmitic.	Stearic.	Behenic.	Total.
I	2.693 g.	—	—	2.693 g.
II	—	1.524 g.	—	1.524.
III	—	2.334	0.375 g.	2.709
IV	—	0.688	0.367	0.955
Total	2.693	4.446	0.742	7.89

Hence the composition of the solid acids is : palmitic acid, 34.15% ; stearic acid, 56.39% ; behenic acid, 9.46%.

Identification of the Liquid Acids.—Liquid acids were examined by the bromine addition method (Jamieson and Baughman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2398). From 5g. of the liquid acids 0.439 g. of hexabromostearic acid was obtained, m. p. 179–80°. The filtrate was washed to remove the excess of bromine and on drying and removing ether, was dissolved in petroleum ether and kept at 0° for 2 hours. The precipitate of tetrabromostearic acid obtained was 1.330 g. and melted at 112–13°. The residue (7.06 g.) was worked out as usual and its bromine content was 41.16%.

The percentage of bromine in the residue is higher than that corresponding to the dibromostearic acid (36.36 %). Hence it is assumed that the same weight as solid tetrabromo and hexabromostearic acids is retained in the residue and then the percentage of different acids calculated.

The composition of liquid acids therefore comes out to be linolenic acid, 6.53% ; linolic acid, 25.15% and oleic acid, 68.28%.

Hence the composition of the mixed acids is : palmitic acid, 13.66% ; stearic acid, 22.55% ; behenic acid, 3.784% ; linolenic acid, 3.918% ; linolic acid, 15.15% ; oleic acid, 40.97%.

Unsaponifiable matter.—This was obtained by extracting the dry soap with ether after treatment with charcoal and crystallisation from alcohol ; it had m.p. 131–32°. When boiled with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate it gave an acetyl derivative, m.p. 118°. It gave all the characteristic colour reactions of phytosterol.

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